

Night Market, an Effective Tool for Urban Development: A Case Study of ‘Reserved’ Night Market in Ore, Nigeria

¹Adeyemi M. Ariyo, ¹Felix K. Omole and ²Emmanuel Gabriel

¹Department of Urban and Regional Planning, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria

²Department of Environmental Management, Kaduna State University, Nigeria

Corresponding Author: gabrielemmycarl@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15012687>

Abstract

This study assessed peculiar characteristics, impact and functionality of Reserved Night market as an effective tool for developing the socio-economic life of the people of Ore and its environs. The research design adopted was a combination of explanatory and descriptive designs. The population size for the study was 3,500 from which a sample size of 5% was taken, resulting to one hundred and seventy-five respondents. Using a systematic sampling technique, one of every 20 persons met in the market was selected during the survey. The results of the research indicated dominance of the age (19 - 39) years. Artisans and self-employed were mostly found in the market between (7 – 10) pm. More students and unemployed youths in the market between (4 - 7) pm. Functions of the market include, cheap commodity, pleasure, business and convenience. However, most traders in the market make more profit at night. Challenges that hindered the functionality of the night market under study were: lack of adequate space for trading activities, inadequate infrastructural facilities, improper waste management, inefficient security services, traffic congestion (vehicular and pedestrian) among others. Therefore, the paper recommends the provision of more trading stalls with adequate facilities, stable electricity, efficient security, proper waste management, as well as, quality accommodation in the market area to meet international standards.

Keywords: Night market, Socioeconomic, Infrastructural facilities, Trading stalls, and Management.

INTRODUCTION

A market is no other place than a specific space, carved out for both buyers and sellers to assemble and exchange goods and services (Basorun, 2004). Market cannot exist without a settlement (population) that it is going to serve and roads (transportation) for easy accessibility. The tripartite relationship bonding market, population and transportation makes them an inseparable trio (Ariyo, 2014). An urban settlement is a place with a relatively large population that has a certain legal status, granted by the National or Provincial Government, and that is associated with specific administrative or Local Government structures (Brockner, 2000). Urban marketing refers to any avenue where people from diverse locations come together for business transactions (Reiner, 1968). Going by this definition, a regional market is a good example of urban market.

Night markets, also known as night bazaars or evening markets are outdoor or indoor markets that

operate at night, typically during the evening or late-night hours. Night markets are stem cells of cities, where non-quantifiable factors such as culture and policy are nucleic acids that carry instruction molding its spatiotemporal configurations (Villaseca, 2021). The concept of night markets traces its roots back to the Tang dynasty in medieval China. Night markets played a central role in Chinese nightlife (Yu, 2004). They were found in corners of large Chinese cities. Stories were formed of how well-known politicians and intellectuals visited night market stall (Yu, 2004). Some notable night markets around the world: In Asia, Taiwanese night markets include; Shihlin, Yilan, Taoyuan, Hsinchu, Taichung among others. Chinese night markets include; Donghuamen Snacks, Guijie Street, Wan among others. There are thousands of night markets in North America, South America, Europe, Australia, and in Africa as well.

However, night markets in Africa include, Fox Market Shed in Johannesburg, The Bay Harbour Market in Hout Bay Cape Town and The Stables Lifestyle Market in Durban, whereas in Nigeria, night markets include, Balogun Market in Lagos, Ariaria Market in Aba and Kurmi Market in Kano among others. The emergence of markets in African countries for example, Nigeria, started at the cities' centers known as the Central Business Districts (C.B.D) and also, at some strategic corners within the cities to facilitate the distribution of commodities produced in different localities around (Basorun, 2004).

In Ondo State, the availability, potential and functionality of night markets have been under-utilized right from the time immemorial, probably due to the belief and culture of the people (Ariyo, 2014). Some people's belief and some parents' advice do not encourage night outing, for instance, there is a popular saying in "Yoruba land", Ondo State inclusive, that '*eniabi ire, kiirinloru*' meaning a responsible person should not be a lover of night outings. This belief and practice discourages engagement in night market in Ondo State. Ariyo in 2014 opined that, the fear of the anti-social occurrences such as pickpocketing, robbery and mugging, harassment and intimidation, public drunkenness, food safety issues, overcrowding and heat-related illnesses and unhygienic conditions associated with the night markets was another major factor discouraging the people from visiting a night market.

However, there are few night markets at some strategic spots within Ondo State, in Akure, for instance, Leo-Junction night market. Nearly all the towns and villages in Ondo State have strategic places or spots where different kinds of night trading take place, such as local bars or drinking joints and restaurants, but the concept of night marketing is wider and more complex than just a drinking spot or a small commercial outlet used as local bar or restaurant at the community center (Ariyo, 2014).

The *Reserved* night market in Ore is a daily market which starts around 3pm and closes around 10:30pm. The market came into existence due to the creation of a Government reserved camp very close to the location of the market from where the market derived its name (*Reserved*). The farmers from the camp usually brought their products to the old Lagos road in Ore for sale to the drivers and

passengers from far and wide, this was how the market sprang up. This night market being studied, apart from being a trading center, is a tourists' center just like *Oke Maria* yearly pilgrims' night market in Oka-Akoko and other notable night markets in Nigeria. *Oke Maria* serves as a three-in-one center; (i) prayer center, (ii) tourist center, and (iii) yearly night market center (Omole, Olanibi, Amodu & Emmanuel, 2013).

This research work x-rayed the significance of *reserved* night market as a veritable tool for urban development. The aim was achieved through the following objectives: investigating the socio-economic attributes of the respondents; operational characteristics of the night market; and in addition, relevant recommendations were made on how to make the night market an international trading and tourist center. However, the scope of this study was restricted to the market users only, that is, the people from Ore and its catchment communities such as Omifon, Bagbe, Orita-Ojo, Kajola/Oju-Irin, Obe, Lasia, Asewele-Korede, Asewele-Oja, Oro, Ominia, Araromi, Oke-Alafia, Olowo, Lamuda among others. This study shows that not much literature has been written on the *Reserved* Night Market in Ore, therefore, this research work is expected to be an eye opener to many researchers, scholars and students.

The works of scholars, particularly, that of Oluwole (2000), and Omole, Owoeye and Ogundiran, (2012) among others have successfully identified two basic classes of market which are distinctive or interrelated. These are daily, and periodic markets. The daily market can be divided into four depending on the time of day the market takes place. These are: (i) Morning markets, (ii) Day Markets, (iii) Night Markets, and (iv) Day/Night Markets (Omole, Lukman & Baki, 2013). Night markets are commonly known as *Pasarmalam* by the locals in Persia, Malaysia and Indonesia, which literally mean night market, "pasar" being related to "bazaar" in Persian or also the meaning "market" in Malay/Indonesian, and "malam" meaning "night". A *pasarmalam* is a street market in Indonesia, Malaysia and Singapore that opens in the evening, usually in residential neighbourhoods (Jordan, David, Andrew, & Marc, 2004). This is similar to what the "Yoruba" in the South West, Nigeria call "Oja-ale".

A lot of scholars have tried to give their own definitions of night market based on their personal

perceptions and reasoning. Some of the arguments of these writers are as follow: Night market is a huge bargain market which includes roadside vendors and sex workers, and retail stores (Ryan & Lilian, 2006). Wendy, a food service provider from Malaysia in the year 2000, said, “Night market is an excellent place for all kinds of sweets and savory snacks, roasted fish, barbequed pork, chicken and other good Malaysia food”. A night market is also a grouping of temporary outdoor stalls operated by petty traders where products are displayed for sale. Night market is an important economic model in cities and the success of night market development is of great significance to the management and development of the cities (Li, Wang & Wang, 2021).

Night market is economically beneficial for regional development because of internalization and globalization of tourism development. In addition, night market is a place for residents to relax and it improves the quality of life of residents because of its characteristics of low price and rich variety. Therefore, research on the night market can offer more broad facilities for residents’ lives (Liu, Chou, & Lin, 2021).

The night market popularity stemmed from the convenience they provide for the local residents to do shopping for their household needs within their residential areas. Thus, they provide an alternative shopping option. Additionally, the night markets, with their friendly and relaxed atmosphere, allow the customers to enjoy the diverse environment, the wide choices of freshly cooked food and fresh vegetables at affordable prices. Trading activity could happen at any time, either during the day or at night. When a transaction takes place at night, then, it is referred to as a night market (Ariyo, 2014). Night market trading activity is contributing to the increase in Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs), which triggers economic growth (Ugulumu, Nestory & Mpsa, 2023).

Night market was defined by Huang, Liou, and Tzeng, (2009) as a trading center during the evening, where small businesses offered a variety of cheap products and cooked food. Night markets was defined as street markets operating at night, mainly in urban or suburban areas that generally tend to have more leisure, shopping, and eating areas (Lee, 2008). Night markets or night bazaars are street markets which operate at night (Yu, 2004). In other words, an urban night market is any

coming together of people (sellers and buyers, visitors and tourists, indigenes and foreigners among others) in a place, usually at urban centers, for business transactions or fun-making, at night. Night market is also a temporary weekly event or activity that usually takes place at available open spaces and on roads or parking lots that are temporary closed to allow for their operations (Khalilah, 2010).

Night markets in Taiwan attracted Taiwanese because of the low prices of the commodities, wide range or variety of products, and the convenient neighbourhood locations (Lee, 2005). Night markets are generally dedicated to more fun catching such as leisure strolling, buying and selling of goods and souvenirs (shopping), arts exhibition and selling of artistic works, patronage to stripping show house or night clubbing, girls hunting, night gambling, sex services and prostitution, patronage to game and cinema houses, patronage to barbeques and bars for eating and drinking, swimming and surfing at pools, than more businesslike day markets. Night markets are also the main targets or sites for anti-social behaviour such as murder, street fight, sexual abuse or rape, drug abuse and dealings, kidnapping and abduction, robbery and swindling, vandalism, to mention but a few (Ariyo, 2014 and Ramello, 2023).

Some scholars even believe that night markets are more conducive for petty traders and young businessmen than day markets. One of such scholars is Hsieh who argued that night markets contend with the demand of people with different occupations than day markets. He further expressed that; night markets are the best places for the beginners and fresh entrepreneurs, to trade because of the favourable atmosphere and enabling environment for petty trading (Hsieh, 2006). He buttressed his points by saying; thousands of Taiwanese youths have started selling different kinds of goods with little capital in virtually all the night markets in Taiwan. Basically, there are two broad types of night markets, these are; (1) Open-air night markets and, (2) Indoor night markets (Hsieh, 2006). The open-air night markets which are also known as outdoor or street night markets are trading activities on the streets at night. These are the commonest types of night markets. While, indoor night markets are the business transactions

at night in an enclosed building or shopping malls (Li, Kong & Yang, 2021).

It has been discovered over time that night markets need more infrastructural facilities than day markets for example, the issue of electricity may not be germane in day markets but inevitable in the night markets. Also, in the issue of security, there is a greater number of police, security dogs, Close-Circuit Televisions (CCTVs), present at major night markets in advanced countries, compared to the contemporary day markets because of the high crime rate associated with night economy (Griffiths, 2003 and Marion, 2004). The importance of public infrastructure consists of economic, social and political terms. Economically, because they are among the basis of industries on which national productivity depends and which absorb very large capital expenditure: Socially, because of great influence on transport, health and others in shaping the life of the people. Politically, because of the collective challenge to enterprise and replacement of public services motive for profit making everywhere made its impact in the aspect (Basorun, 2004). What makes a society

comfortable and habitable is the infrastructure present in such society. As a major link between sources of raw materials and possible market, roads greatly determine the degree of operation of an industry and market within a geographical framework (Basorun, 2004). Threshold population study is also an important aspect of literature issue, that is, the minimum population required to make provision of goods and services minimally profitable, worthwhile and economical. Threshold population justifies the extinction and existence of market. If threshold population falls, the market may go into extinction but if the threshold population increases, the market continues to flourish (Ariyo, 2014).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study area is a nodal town simply known as Ore, the headquarters of Odigbo Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria. Ore has geographical coordinates of 6° 45' 0" North and 4° 52' 0" East.

Figure 1: Map of Nigeria showing the study area in its national, regional and local settings.
 Source: Ondo State Ministry of Housing and Urban Development (2020).

The Odigbo Local Government Area has a total population of 230,351 and land mass of about 1818km² (NPC, 2006). The adjoining Local Government Areas of Odigbo are: Irele, Idanre, Ikale, Ondo West and Ondo East Local Government Areas respectively. Ore is a nodal town because it is passed through by Federal, State and Local roads such as Sagamu/Benin express way, Ondo/Ore Road, Ode-Aye/Okitipupa road, Agbabu/Irele road and so on. As a result of this, it serves as a good commercial hub. Some of the popular streets in Ore are Oniparaga, Sharp-Corner, King Emmanuel, Rainbow, Midway, Adebayo and Mission Road and among others. The 'reserved' night market under study is located along old Lagos Road, very close to the Government *reserved* camp in Ore. This is the reason why it is being referred to as 'reserved' night market.

Methods

The research design adopted was a combination of explanatory and descriptive designs (models). In pursuance of the achievement of the aim and objectives of this research as earlier stated, primary and secondary data were used. The primary sources include: reconnaissance survey of the night market to get acquainted with the existing situation of its infrastructural facilities and administration of structured questionnaire among the market users. Oral interview was also conducted with prominent members of the market community and relevant agencies in relation to the market, so as to get a clearer view of what was going on within the market. The secondary data were obtained from literature materials, such as academic journals, seminar papers, research data, project dissertations, textbooks and internet among others.

For the purpose of this research, the survey questionnaire was divided into two parts, that is, socio-economic attributes of the market users and operational characteristics of the market. Furthermore, hypothesis testing was carried out to confirm the validity of statements about the relationships that exist between night market and testable variables collected on the respondents. The average number of market users per night was discovered to be within the range of 3,000 to 4,000, based on convenience sampling technique. Since the study could not ascertain the actual figure between 3,000 and 4,000, therefore, the mean of

these two figures was calculated to be 3,500, from which a sample size of 5% was taken for this study. This results to one hundred and seventy-five respondents. Similarly, Ugulumu, Nestory and Mpsa (2023), also used convenience sampling technique to get number of respondents for examining factors affecting night market traders' performance in Forodhani night market, Unguja, Tanzania.

Besides, using a systematic sampling technique, one of every 20 persons met in the market was selected during the survey. The night market was divided into two sections, as it was divided by the old Lagos road. One hundred copies of questionnaire were administered in section (I) between 4pm to 7pm because it is actually faster to administer questionnaire in the broad day light than at night and also because it covers a greater proportion of the entire market area, while seventy-five copies of questionnaire were administered in section (II) between 7pm to 10pm. Tables and graphs were used to present, interpret and discuss research findings through SPSS version 21 and Microsoft Excel 2013. However, the first frequency and percentage columns were the data collected in section I of the market between 4pm to 7pm while the second frequency and percentage columns were the data collected in section II between 7pm to 10pm (as seen in Results and Discussion). Prescriptive analysis was used in the recommendation and conclusion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for analysis. Tables and charts were employed to present the magnitude of occurrences of the variables that were obtained. Spearman's correlation technique was employed to test the hypotheses. The tables 1, 2, 3, and 6 have two sets of data, that is, two frequency columns and two percentage columns. The first frequency and percentage columns were the data collected in section I of the market between 4pm to 7pm while the second frequency and percentage columns were the data collected in section II between 7pm to 10pm. Prescriptive analysis was used in the recommendation and conclusion.

Socio-Economic attributes of the Respondents

Table 1 shows that 100 respondents were interviewed between (4-7) pm out of which 58

were buyers and 42 were sellers, while 75 respondents were contacted between (7-10) pm out of which 52 were buyers and 23 were sellers. The greater proportion of the questionnaires were administered in section I, (which covers about 60% of the market land-mass), between 4pm and 7pm because the researchers aimed at covering greater part of the market during the broad day light for it is not easy to administer much questionnaires at night.

Table 1 reveals the dominance of the age brackets of (19-39) years throughout the market period. It can be inferred that this age group had everything it takes, energy and time among others, to withstand the pressure encountered in the market whether during the day or at night. However, the percentage of adolescents (below 18 years) reduced from 25% between (4pm-7pm) to 13.3% between (7-10) pm while the number of youths simultaneously increased from 39% to 53.4% within same periods respectively. With this, it can be deduced that more youths were found in the market at night (7pm-10pm) than in day time (4pm-7pm) because the market exhibited more fun activities at night than day time. The percentage of people age brackets (40 – 60) years found in the market between (4pm-7pm) dropped from 27% to

25.3% at (7pm-10pm). This age group engaged in so many domestic activities between 7pm and 10pm such as cooking especially, women which might be the reason behind their drop in number. The least category of people found in the market was the old people of 60 years and above. What was observed as the reasons for this low turnout of old people in the market were attributed to; lack of adequate strength, poor vision especially at night and availability of younger ones who could run errand for them, among others.

Table 1 shows more students and unemployed youths came to the market between (4-7) pm having 32.8%, than at night between (7-10) pm with 28.8%. This could be due to the fact that most students participated in cooking or reading at night. The highest number of people met in the market between (4-7) pm was the civil servants having 37.9% of the respondents because most of them used the market on their way back from the office. This figure reduced to 23.1% at night. Artisans and self-employed were mostly found in the market between (7-10) pm having 40.4% but very few in the market between (4-7) pm with just 17.2%. This might be because most artisans and self-employed were very busy during the broad day light than at night.

Table 1: Socioeconomic characteristics of respondents

Respondents	Evening		Night	
	Freq.	Percent (4-7pm)	Freq.	Percent (7-10pm)
Category				
Buyers	58	58.0	52	69.3
Sellers	42	42.0	23	30.7
Total	100	100.0	75	100.0
Age of respondents				
< 18	25	25.0	10	13.3
19 – 39	39	39.0	40	53.4
40 – 60	27	27.0	19	25.3
>60	9	9.0	6	8.0
Total	100	100.0	75	100.0
Occupation (Buyers only)				
Unemployed/Students	19	32.8	15	28.8
Artisans/self employed	10	17.2	21	40.4
Civil servants	22	37.9	12	23.1
Others	7	12.1	4	7.7
Total	58	100.0	52	100.0

Source: Authors' field survey, 2019.

In table 2, 5.7% of the respondents said that the average population of market users per night was <1000, 10.9% said the figure was between 1000-2000 while 25.7% said it was between 2001-3000 and 45.7% picked between 3001-4000, 9.1% said it was between 4001-5000. While the remaining 2.9% of the respondents picked above 5000.

Table 2: Average population of market users

No of users/night	Freq	Percent
<1000	10	5.7
1000-2000	19	10.9
2001-3000	45	25.7
3001-4000	80	45.7
4001-5000	16	9.1
> 5000	5	2.9
Total	175	100.0

Source: Authors' field survey, 2019.

Going with this stand, the study agreed that the average population of market users per night was in

the range of 3,001 and 4,000. The reason behind this fair turn-out of people in the night market under study might not be different from the problems encountered in the night market earlier discussed. The findings on socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents agreed with the findings of Ugulumu, Nestory and Mpsa (2023) on factors affecting night market traders' performance in Tanzania.

The major problems as shown in table 3 were; inadequate trading space/stalls with 32.6% of the total respondents, inadequate water and electricity with 18.9%, inefficient security with 14.8%, lack of infrastructure, for example, roads and drainages with 9.7%, improper waste management of 8.6%, low disposable income of 4.0%, lack of affordable accommodation with 4.0%, unstable national economy with 2.3% and, lack of interest in night marketing with 2.3%. With these figures, we concluded that, if the problems of adequate trading stalls, water and electricity are solved, then more than 50% of the problems of the night market under study are solved.

Table 3: Factors limiting night market patronage in Ore, Ondo State

Factors	Freq	Percent
Inadequate trading space/stalls	57	32.6
Inadequate water and electricity supply	33	18.9
Unstable national economy	4	2.3
Improper waste management	15	8.6
Inefficient security	26	14.8
Lack of affordable accommodation	7	4.0
Lack of interest in night marketing	4	2.3
Lack of roads, drainages & parking lots	17	9.7
Low disposable income	7	4.0
Traffic congestion	5	2.8
Total	175	100.0

Source: Authors' field survey, 2019.

Table 4 shows that some traders made good profit per night with 32 respondents (that is, 21 + 11 = 32) out of a total traders of 65, agreed to making as much as between N1,000 – N5,000 profit per night. Only 10 traders out of 65 made a low profit between N1 – N500 per night. With this figure, it was inferred that most traders in the market make more profit at night. However, the findings on factors limiting night market patronage in Ore concurred with the findings of Zoma and Dahani (2022) on characteristics of urban markets in Africa and Ugulumu, Nestory and Mpsa (2023) on factors affecting night market traders' performance in Tanzania.

Table 4: Average profit made by the sellers per night

Profit(N)	Freq	Percent (4-7pm)	Freq	Percent (7-10pm)
1-500	7	16.7	3	13.0
501-1,000	13	31.0	7	30.4
1,001-5,000	21	50.0	11	47.8
5,001-10,000	1	2.3	2	8.8
Above 10,000	-	-	-	-
Total	42	100.0	23	100.0

Source: Authors' field survey, 2019.

Operational Characteristics of the Night Market

Figure 2: Average distance covered by the night market users

Source: Authors field survey, 2019

Figure 3: Reasons for patronage of the night market (Buyers only)

Source: Authors' field survey, 2019.

Figure 2 shows the average distance covered by the respondents. 28% of the respondents interviewed between 4pm and 7pm lived within a distance of < or = 100m radius to the market, 30% came within (101-200)m radius, 15% came within (201- 300)m

radius, 15% came within (301-500)m radius, and 12% came from places over 500m radius to the market. At the other hand, 41.7% of the total respondents met between (7-10)pm came from places of < 100m radius, 25% came within (101-

200)m radius, 16.6% were from (201-300)m radius, 11.7% came within (301-500)m radius, while 5% were from places over 500m radius. In other words, this implies that, the closer one is to the night market, the greater the chance of his/her patronage and benefit of the market and vice-versa (Huang, *et al*, 2009). The study concludes that the greatest proportion of the people found in the market lived within a radius of 500m or less to the market.

Figure 3 shows different reasons why people visited the night market. 35% of the respondents visited between (4-7) pm because of cheap commodity, 10% for pleasure, 40% for business, 10% for convenience while 5% visited for other reasons not specified. Between (7-10) pm, 16.7% said they visited because of cheap commodity, 41.7% for pleasure, 20% for business, and 16.7% for convenience. The percentage of the buyers who visited the night market for cheap raw commodities during the day, dropped from 35% to 16.7% at night, but the percentage of those who visited the market for pleasure increased from 10% to 41.7% within same periods respectively. This implies that, the activities of the night market under study changed from more business-like to more fun-catching as time went on. In addition, *ipso facto*, the study concludes that, the night market under study portrays mostly the characteristics of a day market between (4-7) pm but that of a night market between (7-10) pm. However, the findings on operational characteristics of Ore night market were in agreement with the findings of Zoma and Dahani (2022) on characteristics of urban markets in Africa.

Hypotheses Testing

The hypotheses tested in this study were aimed at confirming the validity of statements about relationships that exist between night market and testable variables collected on respondents. Night market was considered as the dependent variable while other data collected such as occupation and distance covered by the market-users were considered as independent variables. It is meant to find out the effect of the existence of Ore night market on the economic and social development of the people. The figures obtained are presented in contingency tables 5 and 6.

In the first hypothesis tested in table 5, revealed the relationship between the occupation of

the buyers (Socio-demographic attribute of the night market customers) and time of market patronage using Spearman's correlation technique. A correlation coefficient value 0.344 at $P = 0.043$, that is, weak correlation. This explicitly connotes that there is 34.4% relationship between the occupation of the buyers and the time of night market patronage, which changes positively from 4pm to about 10pm. The test result shows that, "the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected while the alternative hypothesis (H_i) is accepted", which means ***there is a significant correlation between the occupation of the people and the time of night market patronage***. Table 1 also justified this by revealing that more civil servants were found in the market between 4pm to 7pm while self-employed and artisans dominated the market at night between 7pm to 10pm. In other words, everybody benefits from the night market, that is, the night market creates employment opportunities for the jobless people and services for those that are gainfully employed.

In the second hypothesis tested as shown in table 6, the relationship between the occupation of the buyers (Socio-demographic attribute of the night market customers) and distance covered by the market users using Spearman's correlation technique. With a correlation coefficient value 0.571 at $P < 0.001$, the null hypothesis stated is countered (as shown in table 6). This shows average distance covered by the market users clearly that 57.1% variation in occupations of buyers (night market customers) results in a positive increase in the average distance covered to the night market from below 100m to beyond 500m. The test result implies that, "the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected while the alternative hypothesis (H_i) is accepted", which literally means ***there is a significant relationship between the occupation of the people and the average distance covered by the market users radius of < 500m***. In other words, this implies that, the closer one is to the night market, the more one engages in or benefits from the night market and the more one's socio-economic life is improved.

The data gathered from oral interviews also revealed that, most people living within the radius of <500m to the market depend solely on the market for their livelihood, that is, most of them are sellers in the market.

Table 5: Nonparametric Correlation Analysis of the Occupation of the buyers against the time of market patronage

			Occupation of the Buyers	Time of market patronage
Spearman's rho	Occupation of the Buyers	Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed) N	1.000 .043 35	.344* .043 35
	Time of market patronage	Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed) N	.344* .043 35	1.000 .043 35

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Author's Computation with IBM SPSS 22, 2019.

Table 6: Nonparametric Correlation Analysis of the Occupation of the buyers against the average distance covered

			Occupation of the Buyers	Distance Covered
Spearman's rho	Occupation of the Buyers	Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed) N	1.000 .000 35	.571** .000 35
	Distance Covered	Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed) N	.571** .000 35	1.000 .000 35

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Author's Computation with IBM SPSS 22, 2019.

CONCLUSION

Ore Reserved Night market is found in the category of "Day/Night market", the 4th category according to Omole (2003) because the results in figure 2 showed that the market possessed the attributes of a day market between (4pm-7pm) and that of a night market between (7pm-10pm). That is, most people visited the market for business purposes between 4pm-7pm while most people patronized the market for pleasure/fun-making between 7pm-10pm. The average profit made per seller per night was believed to be between N1,000- N5,000 according to (table 6). As a result of this, this study concluded that, of a truth, the night market under study has influenced the people's life positively in terms of income generation through economic revitalization and job creation, that is, Ore-night market was indeed an effective tool for urban development both socially and economically; socially, because it served as a fun-catching and tourist center, and economically, because it created employment opportunities for the people, most especially, jobless youths but there is always a need for improvement in everything man does.

The paper recommends the provision of adequate trading stalls for the traders because it was discovered that there was a severe inadequacy of trading stalls in the market under study. This has led to illegal shops/shanties being built all over the market area. These trading stalls include: 'open and close stalls', shopping complexes, kiosks, malls et cetera, for the seller's utilization at low rent-fee. To achieve this, government, private companies and wealthy individuals partnership is needed as government alone cannot do the task. The provision of more trading stalls is highly essential because it commands a very high magnitude on the development of the market as shown in table 3.

Another recommendation is the provision of infrastructural facilities to address the poor condition of infrastructure such as water, electricity, roads, drainages and parking lots among others. However, hospitals/clinics should not be far from the market in case of emergency. Fire service stations should be provided very close to the market in case of fire disaster. Communication services should also be made available. There is a need for partnership between Government and

private organizations in the provision of the needed infrastructure and they can also collaborate in rehabilitating, repairing or renewing the worn-out ones. The old Lagos road in particular, along which the market is situated, should be broadened and rehabilitated to ease vehicular and pedestrian movement.

Security challenge is a national issue, therefore, the paper recommends more security personnel, such as, police, army, civil defense, vigilante group, security dogs and CCTV among others, to beef up the security in the market area. This can be justified according to Griffiths, (2003) "night markets are more prone to security threats than their contemporary day markets". All arms of security forces must be readily and fully on ground to beef-up the security of the night market under study.

The issue of good sanitary measures within the market must be taken with optimum seriousness. That is, waste bins, public toilets, waste collection vehicles and trained waste managers are recommended to curb the problems of improper waste disposal and management within the market. If the waste generated in the market is adequately managed, there will be no cause for alarm over any disease epidemic such as cholera outbreak and chicken pox et cetera.

In addition, another recommendation is the provision of quality accommodation for the market users. In other words, building of hotels, brothels, motels, bars and club houses, parks and recreational centers among others, around the night market area by the government and wealthy individuals are highly recommended. This will encourage and attract the traveling traders, visitors, tourists, foreigners and researchers and the likes to the night market. Furthermore, provision of neon lights, disco lights, security lights and cool music are recommended because they serve significant roles in attracting people towards the night market. But, sellers should not cause noise pollution with their music. These are supposed to be done by the shop owners (sellers) to woo customers.

Furthermore, the provision of credit facilities by Government and well-to-do people in the society should create credit facilities at no or little interest rate to encourage young and petty traders in the market, by so doing, creating an enabling environment for the trading activities to thrive. Government should also encourage the young

entrepreneurs through positive policies such as: tax free and giving of grants. Creation of awareness and advertisement on the social media for examples, radio, TV and phone, among others, are also recommended by this study.

If the recommendations stated are properly implemented, the identified problems of the market would be tackled and Ore night market will become a tourist center like Richmond Night Market (USA), which features more than 400 booths and attracts in excess of 30,000 people per night (total attendance in 2005 was almost two million). Night It Up! (USA), formerly Toronto Night Market and Asian Night Market, has been and continued to be Power Unit Youth Organization's flagship project, attracting hundreds of thousands to a three-day celebration of Asian food and culture in Markham, Ontario (attendance was over 130,000 in 2017) and Yu, 2004 among others.

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